

pH-metric Studies on Quaternary Mixed Ligand Complex Formation of Ni(II)

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Mixed ligand complexes of the type MABC, where M=Ni(II), A=oxalic (OX), malonic (MALN) or phthalic (PHA) acids, B=ethylenediamine (en) or 1,2-diaminopropane (pn) and C=aminoacetic acid (gly) have been investigated by potentiometric titration technique. Evidence is given for the stepwise addition of B and C to the initially formed MA complex, resulting in ternary (MAB) and quaternary (MABC) complex formation respectively. Formation constants ($\log K_{MABC}$) and the free energies of formation (ΔF°) for the quaternary systems have been calculated at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The order of stability in terms of diamine have been found to be as $pn > en$.

THE binary as well as the ternary complexes of transition metals have been extensively investigated. Scanty references are, however, available on quaternary systems such as Fe(III)-NTA-EDTA-phenol¹ and UO₂(II)-A-B-C^{2,3} (A, B and C are the different dibasic acids). It has, therefore, been thought worthwhile to investigate quaternary systems involving some other transition metals.

The potentiometric studies of the quaternary system Ni(II)-dicarboxylic acids (H₂A)-diamines (Am)-gly (where H₂A=oxalic(OX), malonic (MALN), phthalic(PHA) acids, Am=ethylenediamine(en), 1,2-diaminopropane(pn), have been carried out. The results of these studies have been discussed in the present communication.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals used were either of BDH (A.R.) or S. Merck (G.R.) grade. The stock solution of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O was prepared in double-distilled water and the metal was estimated as Ni(C₄H₇O₂N₂)₂⁴. The solutions of ligands oxalic, malonic, phthalic, glycine and dihydrochlorides of ethylenediamine and 1,2-diaminopropane were prepared by dissolving the appropriate weighed amount of the respective materials in double-distilled water. The concentrations of the ligand solutions were further checked by potentiometric titration using 0.1M KOH.

Instrument and Methods :

The pH-titrations were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ (maintained thermostatically) with the help of Philips Precision pH-meter (PR 9405M) standardised against 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen-phthalate.

The total volume of the solution (50 ml), ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$ KNO₃) and the concentration in metal and ligands ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) were kept constant at the beginning of the titration. All the titrations were performed in duplicate to establish the reproducibility of the measurements.

The following sets of solutions were titrated and the pH units were plotted against m (m=moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligands) :

1. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ ;
2. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA/gly ;
3. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) en.2H⁺/pn.2H⁺ ;
4. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA/gly ;
5. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) en.2H⁺/pn.2H⁺ ;
6. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) en.2H⁺ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA/gly ;
7. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) pn.2H⁺ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA/gly ;
8. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) en. 2H⁺ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) gly ;
9. 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) Ni(NO₃)₂ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) pn.2H⁺ + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) OX/MALN/PHA + 10 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) gly.

Calculations :

The dissociation constants of the ligands (OX, MALN, PHA, en.2H⁺ and gly) were determined by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁵ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS
 $t=25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu=0.1M$ KNO₃

Ligand	pK_1	pK_2
Oxalic acid (OX)	1.54 ± 0.19	4.10 ± 0.06
Malonic acid (MALN)	2.73 ± 0.10	5.34 ± 0.09
Phthalic acid (PHA)	3.03 ± 0.09	5.60 ± 0.09
Ethylenediamine (en)	6.96 ± 0.02	10.01 ± 0.07
1,2-diaminopropane (pn)	$6.91 \pm 0.03^*$	$9.78 \pm 0.02^*$
Glycine (gly)	9.66 ± 0.05	—

* value taken from the literature⁶.

The pK values of $pn.2H^+$ have been taken from the literature⁶.

The formation constants of the quaternary complexes were calculated by employing the method of Thompson and Loraas⁷. The free energies of formation (ΔF°) were calculated by the following expression :

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K_{MABC}$$

where R = gas constant (1.987 K cal/mole/deg.)
 T = temperature in absolute degree

and K_{MABC} = overall formation constant of the quaternary complex.

Results and Discussion

The curves a (gly) and b ($en.2H^+$) (Fig. 1) give inflections at $m=1$ which in the case of gly is ill-defined.

In the system $Ni(II)-en.2H^+/OX$ the inflection at $m=2$ (Fig. 1, curve e, g) and at $m=1$ in the case of $Ni(II)-gly$ (Fig. 1, curve d) may be attributed to the formation of 1:1 binary species. The inflection at $m=3$ (Fig. 1, curve e, g) in the case of $Ni(II)-en.2H^+/OX$, and at $m=2$ (Fig. 1, curve d) in the case of $Ni(II)-gly$ systems at higher pH may be ascribed to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1:1 binary complex into 1:2 $Ni(II)-en.2H^+/OX/gly$ complex.

The curves f, h and i (Fig. 1) represent the 1:1:1 $Ni(II)-en-gly$, $Ni(II)-OX-gly$ and $Ni(II)-OX-en$ systems respectively.

Curve i (Fig. 1) for 1:1:1 $Ni(II)-OX-en$ system overlaps the curve e for 1:1 $Ni(II)-OX$ system up to $m=2$ in the lower pH -range indicating the preference of OX for metal ion in the initial stages. The two inflections at $m=2$ and $m=4$ may be attributed to the successive stepwise addition of OX and $en.2H^+$ to the metal ion resulting in the formation of 1:1:1 $Ni(II)-OX-en$ complex. The non-superimposable nature of the composite curve T' (drawn by adding the horizontal distances of the curves for 1:1 $Ni(II)-OX$ system and $en.2H^+$), in the region of ternary complex formation further supports the existence of a mixed ligand ternary species.

Fig. 1.

Curve a—gly
 „ b— $en.2H^+$
 „ c—OX
 „ d—1:1 Ni-gly
 „ e—1:1 Ni- $en.2H^+$
 „ f—1:1:1 Ni- $en.2H^+$ -gly
 „ g—1:1 Ni-OX
 „ h—1:1:1 Ni-OX-gly
 „ i—1:1:1 Ni-OX- $en.2H^+$
 „ j—1:1:1:1 Ni-OX- $en.2H^+$ -gly
 „ T & T'—Composite curves
 → indicates the appearance of turbidity

The addition of the primary and the secondary ligands to the metal ion resulting in the formation of the biligand species may be expressed as :

Similarly in the case of $Ni(II)-OX-gly$ and $Ni(II)-en-gly$ systems OX and $en.2H^+$ respectively act as primary ligand and glycine as a secondary one.

Curve j (Fig. 1) representing 1:1:1:1 $Ni(II)-OX-en-gly$ system, in the initial stages, superimposes the

curve g for 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX system up to $m \approx 2$ and curve i for 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-en up to $m \approx 4$. This superimposition of the quaternary curve j undoubtedly indicates the behaviour of OX and en.2H⁺ as primary and the secondary ligands. The addition of the tertiary ligand-glycine to the intermediate 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-en species, however, appears to occur afterwards. Thus the inflections at $m=2$, $m=4$ and $m=5$ in curve j may respectively be attributed to the stepwise addition of OX, (to the metal ion) en.2H⁺ and gly (to the intermediate 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-en complex) resulting in the formation of a soluble triligand or quaternary 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-en-gly species. The intermediate step showing the addition of en.2H⁺ to the binary Ni(II)-OX complex is evidenced by the superimposition of the quaternary curve j with the ternary curve i for Ni(II)-OX-en.2H⁺ system up to $m=4$. The inflection at $m=4$ indicating the step of addition of en.2H⁺ is, however, not observed in the quaternary curve.

The non-appearance of the precipitate and the non-superimposable nature of the composite curve T (drawn by adding the horizontal distances of the curves for 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-en and gly) further support the formation of the quaternary species.

In Fig. 2, the curves e and g (respectively for 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX and Ni(II)-pn.2H⁺), f and i (respectively for 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-pn-gly and Ni(II)-OX-pn) and curve j, (for 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-OX-pn-gly) being identical in nature to the corresponding systems involving en 2H⁺, may be interpreted in a similar manner.

The quaternary systems involving other dicarboxylic acids (MALN, PHA), diamine (en or pn) and glycine have also been studied but only representative curves for the systems involving oxalic acid and en pn have been given, others being identical are omitted for the brevity's sake. The formation of triligand species in all these cases has, however, been indicated on the basis of potentiometric titrations and the analysis of the data.

Fig. 2.

- Curve a—gly
- " b—pn.2H⁺
- " c—OX
- " d—1 : 1 Ni-gly
- " e—1 : 1 Ni-pn.2H⁺
- " f—1 : 1 : 1 Ni-pn.2H⁺-gly
- " g—1 : 1 Ni-OX
- " h—1 : 1 : 1 Ni-OX-gly
- " i—1 : 1 : 1 Ni-OX-pn.2H⁺
- " j—1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Ni-OX-pn.2H⁺-gly
- " T & T'—Composite Curves
- " → indicates the appearance of turbidity

The calculation for the stepwise addition of diamine/gly and the overall formation constants for the quaternary species at 25 ± 1° have been calculated and are recorded in Table 2. The free

TABLE 2—At 25 ± 1°C

Quaternary systems	log K _{MA}	log K _{MAB}	log K _{MABC}	Overall stability constants	Overall ΔF° K cal/mole
Ni-OX-en-gly	5.3*	7.38 ± 0.06	4.52 ± 0.10	17.20	-23.443
Ni-OX-pn-gly	5.3*	7.48 ± 0.15	4.72 ± 0.20	17.50	-23.852
Ni-MALN-en-gly	4.74*	6.35 ± 0.14	4.08 ± 0.19	14.57	-19.858
Ni-MALN-pn-gly	4.14*	6.45 ± 0.15	4.12 ± 0.12	14.71	-20.049
Ni-PHA-en-gly	3.38 ± 0.18	7.44 ± 0.18	5.43 ± 0.20	16.25	-22.148
Ni-PHA-pn-gly	3.38 ± 0.18	7.72 ± 0.20	5.20 ± 0.18	16.30	-22.216

* values taken from the literature⁹.

energies of formation (ΔF°) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ have also been evaluated.

A comparison of the overall formation constants ($\log K_{MABC}$) given in Table 2 indicate the order of stability of the quaternary complexes in terms of secondary ligands as $pn > en$ which follows the order of their basicities.

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